
EVALUATING PARALLEL GRID SEARCH FOR ARIMA HYPERPARAMETER SELECTION IN FINANCIAL TIME SERIES

A PREPRINT

 Kael Siebra de Lima

Department of Computer Science
Federal University of Ceará
Russas, Ceará - Brazil
kaelsiebra@alu.ufc.br

 Cenez Araújo Rezende

Department of Computer Science
Federal University of Ceará
Russas, Ceará - Brazil
cenezaraujo@ufc.br

March 5, 2026

ABSTRACT

Financial forecasting requires scalable time series modeling pipelines that balance predictive accuracy and computational cost. Although ARIMA remains widely used, exhaustive hyperparameter search becomes a major bottleneck in operational settings. This work proposes an automated ARIMA pipeline integrating stationarity testing with parallelized grid search for parameter selection. The study evaluates the computational and predictive impact of parallel hyperparameter optimization within a reproducible forecasting framework, using three Brazilian stocks from distinct market sectors (energy, utilities, and banking) spanning horizons from six months to eight years. Results show that parallelization achieves a geometric mean speedup of $1.74\times$, reaching up to $6.58\times$ in medium-length series, while maintaining forecasting accuracy below 3% MAPE for medium-term horizons. Analysis based on Amdahl's law indicates that parallel efficiency is strongly dependent on problem scale, with parallelizable fractions ranging from below 10% in very long series to over 70% in medium-length scenarios, where performance gains are most substantial. These findings demonstrate that parallel grid search can reduce computational costs in ARIMA deployment without compromising predictive performance, particularly when applied to datasets of sufficient scale.

Keywords ARIMA · Hyperparameter Optimization · Parallel Computing · Time Series Forecasting

1 Introduction

Time series are sequences of observations recorded at regular intervals, describing the evolution of a given phenomenon over time. Examples include asset prices, regional temperature variations, and demographic counts [Brockwell and Davis, 2016]. In this context, the Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average model (ARIMA) is widely used for forecasting because of its practicality and computational efficiency [Petropoulos et al., 2022].

The ARIMA model generalizes the Autoregressive Moving Average model (ARMA) and can handle non-stationary series, that is, series whose statistical properties such as mean and variance change over time [Box et al., 2015]. Although ARIMA is computationally lightweight compared to deep learning approaches, hyperparameter selection through exhaustive search becomes computationally expensive as dataset size increases. Furthermore, manual configuration requires statistical expertise that may limit reproducibility and scalability.

This study proposes an automated ARIMA execution pipeline with parallelized grid search for parameter selection. The objective is to evaluate the computational and predictive impact of parallel hyperparameter optimization within a reproducible forecasting framework, evaluating scenarios where parallelism considerably improves computational performance. In this work, model selection is based on minimization of the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). After parameter identification, the final model is fitted and evaluated through rolling one-step ahead forecasts.

Section 2 reviews theoretical concepts, Section 3 summarizes related work, Section 4 details the methodology, Section 5 presents results, Section 6 discusses the identified limitations, and Section 7 concludes the paper.¹

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Time Series Properties

A time series is classified as stationary when its statistical properties remain unchanged over time. According to Priestley [1988], a time series X_t is categorized as strictly stationary when the joint probability distribution of $\{X_{t_1}, X_{t_2}, \dots, X_{t_n}\}$ is equal to that of $\{X_{t_1+k}, X_{t_2+k}, \dots, X_{t_n+k}\}$, where k is any integer and t_1, t_2, \dots, t_n is any set of times. A weakly stationary series, normally called simply stationary, satisfies this condition only for the first two moments, requiring constant mean, finite and constant variance, and an autocovariance function that depends only on temporal lag.

In time series, a trend corresponds to a gradual change in the level of the series over time, reflecting persistent shifts in its mean. Because a trend implies changes in statistical properties, a series cannot be stationary when one is present. Trends may be either deterministic or stochastic. Deterministic trends follow a predictable pattern and are modeled using mathematical functions, whereas stochastic trends evolve randomly and typically require differencing to achieve stationarity [Hyndman and Athanasopoulos, 2018].

2.2 ARIMA Model

ARIMA comprises three components: the Autoregressive (AR) part of order p , the differencing component d to achieve stationarity, and the Moving Average (MA) part of order q . An ARIMA(p, d, q) process can be written as

$$\varphi(B)y_t = \phi(B)\nabla^d y_t = \theta_0 + \theta(B)\varepsilon_t, \quad (1)$$

where $\nabla = 1 - B$ is the difference operator, $\phi(B)$ is called the autoregressive operator, $\varphi(B) = \phi(B)\nabla^d$ is the generalized autoregressive operator, being non-stationary, and $\theta(B)$ is the moving average operator [Box et al., 2015].

The ARIMA methodology consists of three stages: determining the differencing order d through stationarity testing, selecting AR and MA orders via exhaustive grid search or information criteria, and model fitting via maximum likelihood. While the first and third stages are inherently sequential, the second stage is embarrassingly parallel because each (p, q) candidate can be evaluated independently. This property motivates the parallelization strategy adopted in Section 4.

Traditional ARIMA modeling uses the Autocorrelation Function (ACF) and Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF) plots to help determine an appropriate (p, d, q) order. The ACF shows correlations between observations at different lags, enabling the identification of temporal dependence patterns. In contrast, the PACF measures the partial correlation at a given lag, controlling for the effects of intermediate lags [Nielsen, 2006].

2.3 Parameter Selection and Grid Search

The differencing order d is selected via the Augmented Dickey–Fuller test. The null hypothesis assumes the presence of a unit root, which indicates non-stationarity. Rejecting the null implies stationarity [Fuller, 1995].

Grid search exhaustively evaluates combinations of (p, d, q) and selects the model minimizing AIC [Bergstra and Bengio, 2012]. A lower AIC indicates a better trade-off between goodness of fit and model complexity.

2.4 Parallel Computing

Parallel computing distributes independent tasks across multiple processing units to reduce execution time [Hennessy and Patterson, 2017]. The theoretical speedup obtained by parallelizing an algorithm is bounded by Amdahl’s law, as overhead from synchronization and task management limits scalability [Höfing and Haunschmid, 2017]. The speedup is defined as

$$S_p = \frac{T_s}{T_p}, \quad (2)$$

where T_s is the execution time of the sequential version of the algorithm and T_p is the execution time of its parallel version [Bakos, 2016].

¹This manuscript is currently under review for journal publication.

Amdahl’s Law is represented by

$$S(N) = \frac{1}{(1 - f) + \frac{f}{N}}, \quad (3)$$

where $S(N)$ is the expected speedup when using N processing units, f denotes the fraction of the workload that can be parallelized, and $(1 - f)$ is the inherently serial part of the algorithm [Amdahl, 1967, Hill and Marty, 2008].

3 Related Work

Classical ARIMA models remain relevant despite the rise of deep learning approaches for time series forecasting. Several comparative studies have evaluated ARIMA against modern neural architectures to understand their respective strengths and limitations.

Yamak et al. [2020] compared ARIMA against LSTM and GRU networks using Bitcoin price data. Surprisingly, ARIMA achieved superior accuracy with a MAPE of 2.7% and RMSE of 302.53, outperforming both recurrent architectures. The authors attributed this outcome to the limited dataset size, which prevented deep learning models from leveraging their capacity effectively. Similarly, Kobiela et al. [2022] conducted experiments on NASDAQ stock data and found that ARIMA outperformed LSTM across all forecasting horizons except one-day predictions, with performance advantages increasing for longer time windows.

While these findings suggest ARIMA’s continued competitiveness, computational efficiency remains a concern. Menculini et al. [2021] evaluated ARIMA alongside Prophet, CNN, and LSTM for wholesale food price forecasting in Italy. Although deep learning models achieved the highest accuracy, their computational costs and hyperparameter tuning times were prohibitive. ARIMA provided a favorable accuracy-efficiency trade-off, outperforming Prophet while remaining significantly faster than neural approaches.

Given ARIMA’s computational bottleneck lies in parameter search, parallelization offers a natural optimization strategy. Vilca-Tinta et al. [2024] demonstrated this approach for energy consumption forecasting in Peru, implementing domain decomposition with parallel grid search over ARIMA orders (p, d, q) using AIC as the selection criterion. Their experiments showed speedup scaling gradually with core count, though evaluation was limited to a single application domain without analysis across varying time horizons.

Recognizing that statistical and deep learning methods capture complementary patterns, hybrid architectures have emerged as an active research direction. Shah et al. [2022] surveyed the landscape of ARIMA-ANN combinations, identifying a common paradigm: ARIMA captures linear dynamics while neural components model residual nonlinearities. Recent instantiations include ARIMA-LSTM with moving average decomposition [Saleti et al., 2024], ARIMA-GARCH-LSTM pipelines for volatility-adjusted forecasting [Mehtarizadeh et al., 2025], and attention-enhanced BiLSTM-ARIMA-XGBoost ensembles under inverse-error weighting [Zhao et al., 2025]. Multi-component frameworks combining ARIMA with RNN and LightGBM have extended this paradigm to high-dimensional datasets [Alarbi et al., 2025], while broader surveys spanning LSTM, GRU, SVM, and temporal convolutional networks confirm the effectiveness of linear-nonlinear decomposition across asset classes [Pokou et al., 2024]. However, these hybrid models exacerbate the challenge of hyperparameter optimization. Beyond ARIMA’s (p, d, q) orders, practitioners must tune network architectures, training procedures, and ensemble weights, substantially expanding the search space and motivating automated selection strategies.

Despite progress on ARIMA parallelization and hybrid architectures, to the best of our knowledge, no prior work has systematically evaluated the speedup–accuracy trade-off across multiple time scales for financial forecasting. Existing automated ARIMA implementations rely on heuristic search strategies that may converge to suboptimal configurations or fail entirely on certain datasets. This work addresses both gaps through a reproducible automated pipeline with empirical evidence across three Brazilian stocks over varying series lengths, demonstrating when parallel grid search provides practical benefits and where its limitations emerge.

4 Methodology

4.1 Computational Environment and Data

The pipeline was implemented in Python 3.12.5 using statsmodels 0.14.2 [Foundation, 2025, Perktold et al., 2024]. Experiments were executed on a system equipped with a six-core Intel Core i5-11400F processor and 16GB RAM running Windows 10.

Financial time series data were retrieved using the yfinance library, which provides programmatic access to historical market data from Yahoo Finance [Aroussi, 2025]. The selected assets were Petróleo Brasileiro S.A. Petrobras

Figure 1: Execution flow of the proposed pipeline.

Preferred Shares (PETR4), Transmissora Aliança de Energia Elétrica S.A. (TAEEl1), and Itaú Unibanco S.A. (ITUB4), representing distinct sectors of the Brazilian stock market, namely energy, utilities, and banking. Daily closing prices denominated in Brazilian Real were used for all experiments. No intraday data were considered.

4.2 Data Preprocessing and Experimental Intervals

The preprocessing stage consisted of verifying data integrity, handling potential missing values, and organizing the series chronologically. Missing observations, when present, were removed to preserve consistency in model fitting.

Three time intervals were chosen for training and forecasting. The first, being very long, with an eight-year period, ranges from June 16, 2017, to June 16, 2025. The second, being long, goes from June 16, 2022, to June 16, 2025, with a duration of three years. Finally, a six-month dataset, being medium, from December 16, 2024, to June 16, 2025. Each interval was independently evaluated to analyze the impact of dataset size on forecasting accuracy and computational performance.

For each configuration, the data were partitioned into training and test sets using an 80 percent and 20 percent split, respectively. The training set was used for model selection and parameter estimation, while the test set was reserved exclusively for out-of-sample evaluation.

Figure 1 illustrates each step of the pipeline execution. First, data for the user’s requested asset is collected and a validation is executed: if any NaN values are present, they are dropped and the gaps left are filled with data from the previous or next available day. If the amount of filled gaps surpasses the amount of non-missing data, the execution halts, as proceeding would lead to inaccurate results. Otherwise, execution proceeds to the data preprocessing step, where the dataset is partitioned into training and test sets. Following this, the ADF test and grid search are executed, defining the model order and initiating the fitting step. Finally, prediction results and model insights are returned to the user, including the selected order, AIC, execution time, a prediction versus real values chart, and stationarity test results, after which the execution ends.²

4.3 Differencing and Hyperparameter Search Strategy

Stationarity was assessed using the Augmented Dickey–Fuller test. The null hypothesis assumes the presence of a unit root, indicating non-stationarity.

If the null hypothesis could not be rejected, first-order differencing was applied. The procedure was repeated iteratively, up to a maximum of three differences, until stationarity was achieved or the maximum differencing level was reached. The resulting differencing order defined the parameter d in the ARIMA(p, d, q) specification. This automated procedure ensures consistent preprocessing across all assets and intervals.

Hyperparameter selection was conducted using an exhaustive grid search over the parameters p and q . Both parameters were explored within the interval $[0, 5]$, resulting in at most $6 \times 3 \times 6 = 108$ different parameter combinations. Each candidate ARIMA model was fitted to the training data using maximum likelihood estimation and model quality was

²The source code used in this study is available at: <https://github.com/kaelkdd/arima-plgs>

evaluated using the Akaike Information Criterion. The parameter combination yielding the lowest AIC was selected as the optimal specification.

The grid search process is computationally intensive because each candidate requires model fitting and likelihood optimization. Therefore, this stage constitutes the primary computational bottleneck in the pipeline.

4.4 Parallelization and Experimental Design

To reduce execution time during hyperparameter selection we implemented a parallelized grid search over candidate (p, q) combinations using Python’s library `joblib` [joblib developers, 2025]. Each (p, q) candidate is an independent task and tasks were executed concurrently across available CPU cores. Workload distribution employed task chunking to reduce scheduling overhead and to group multiple candidate evaluations within a single process, mitigating inter-process communication costs [Acar et al., 2016]. The parallel backend used was `loky`, and experiments reported in this manuscript used `n_jobs=6`, which corresponds to all six logical cores of an Intel Core i5-11400F, and `batch_size="auto"`. The batch size parameter, set to "auto", allows `joblib` to dynamically determine optimal chunk sizes based on the number of available workers and the total number of tasks, balancing parallelization benefits against inter-process communication overhead.

Computational efficiency was measured through speedup and forecast accuracy was assessed using: Mean Absolute Error (MAE), which calculates the mean of absolute errors between real and predicted values; Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE), which calculates the percentage of error relative to real values; and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which also measures the difference between real and estimated values, but assigns greater weight to larger errors.

To enable a fair comparison, sequential and parallel implementations were executed under identical conditions and the same model selection rule was used (AIC minimization). Timings were measured with `time.perf_counter()` and each timing configuration was repeated five times under controlled conditions. Reported timing results use *mean ± standard deviation*. Forecast accuracy metrics are reported as single values because the ARIMA fitting procedure via maximum likelihood estimation is deterministic for fixed data ordering, so forecast metrics do not vary across repetitions.

After selecting the optimal parameter set, the final ARIMA model was fitted to the training data. Forecasting was performed using a rolling one-step-ahead strategy. In this approach, the model generates a one-step prediction for the next observation in the test set. After the true value becomes available, it is appended to the training data, and the model is refitted before generating the subsequent prediction. Although computationally demanding due to repeated refitting, this method provides a realistic evaluation of predictive performance under sequential information availability. We therefore analyze computational performance both empirically and analytically using Amdahl’s law to estimate the parallel fraction and to identify dominant sources of overhead (process startup, chunking choice, and sequential refitting).

5 Empirical Results

5.1 Forecast Accuracy

It is observed in Table 1 that ITUB4 and PETR4 exhibit the highest MAPE values for the long and very long periods. This result indicates that ARIMA’s forecasting accuracy degrades on extended time series. The effect is amplified by the high liquidity and pronounced sensitivity of these assets to political and macroeconomic events, which increases nonstationarity and reduces predictive performance. Figure 2a and Figure 2b illustrate predictions made by ARIMA for the very long and long periods for TAEE11 and PETR4, respectively.

By contrast, TAEE11 shows the lowest MAPE for the very long and long periods, with values of 3.59% and 4.49%, respectively. The comparatively lower volatility of this asset, typical of the electricity sector and of instruments favored by conservative investors, yields more stable error rates under ARIMA modeling. This suggests that low-volatility assets may be particularly well-suited to ARIMA-based forecasting pipelines.

For ITUB4 and TAEE11, the long period produced higher error percentages than the very long period. This outcome may reflect specific macroeconomic events within the three-year window, since the interval considered includes post COVID-19 volatility that affected market behavior.

The medium-duration interval produced the lowest RMSE and MAE and was the most precise overall. In this interval all assets achieved MAPE below 3%. These results indicate that ARIMA adapts more reliably to short, recent windows where seasonality and trend components are more stable and easier to capture.

Table 1: Results obtained in forecasts by the ARIMA model for assets ITUB4, PETR4 and TAEE11.

Asset	Period	Order	AIC	RMSE	MAE	MAPE
ITUB4	Very long	(3,0,2)	1173.49	3.86	2.91	10.92%
ITUB4	Long	(2,1,2)	196.32	4.38	3.44	12.17%
ITUB4	Medium	(0,1,0)	99.52	0.74	0.60	1.80%
PETR4	Very long	(4,1,5)	221.30	3.25	2.61	8.84%
PETR4	Long	(2,1,2)	714.01	2.99	2.38	7.72%
PETR4	Medium	(2,1,2)	140.51	0.96	0.76	2.63%
TAEE11	Very long	(3,1,3)	94.16	1.47	1.12	3.59%
TAEE11	Long	(2,1,3)	182.66	1.81	1.42	4.49%
TAEE11	Medium	(1,1,2)	68.46	0.86	0.69	2.08%

Note: AIC is only used to make comparisons between model orders in the same data and period group.

Figure 2c shows that the model can produce accurate forecasts at many points, but it has difficulty capturing abrupt price changes and therefore reproduces such transitions with a lag.

5.2 Computational Performance

The grid search was executed both sequentially and in parallel, with each configuration run 5 times to assess variability. Peak speedups reached $6.58\times$ and the geometric mean speedup across all workloads was $1.74\times$, indicating that performance gains were concentrated in medium-sized time series. No differences were observed between the ARIMA orders selected across runs.

Table 2 shows that, for the very long eight-year interval, speedup is generally negligible except for TAEE11. This behavior is due to the large dataset size and to overhead costs. Although parallel overhead reduces net speedup, the primary computational bottleneck remains model fitting itself. The rolling forecast requires sequential refitting for each test point, which limits the portion of execution time that can benefit from parallel hyperparameter search.

Table 2: Processing time performance in pipeline executions with sequential and parallel grid search.

Asset	Period	Serial time (s)	Parallel time (s)	Speedup (x)
ITUB4	Very long	471.39 \pm 0.94	448.93 \pm 0.82	1.05 \pm 0.003
ITUB4	Long	64.79 \pm 0.12	46.41 \pm 1.37	1.40 \pm 0.04
ITUB4	Medium	10.71 \pm 0.09	2.12 \pm 1.64	6.58 \pm 2.50
PETR4	Very long	606.13 \pm 1.34	567.49 \pm 0.54	1.07 \pm 0.002
PETR4	Long	56.21 \pm 0.10	36.80 \pm 1.68	1.53 \pm 0.06
PETR4	Medium	11.78 \pm 0.04	4.47 \pm 1.55	2.82 \pm 0.66
TAEE11	Very long	397.60 \pm 7.22	370.15 \pm 9.95	1.07 \pm 0.02
TAEE11	Long	71.88 \pm 0.10	53.42 \pm 1.65	1.35 \pm 0.03
TAEE11	Medium	12.56 \pm 0.15	4.03 \pm 1.58	3.40 \pm 0.90

Speedup is more effective on shorter intervals where overhead is smaller relative to per-model fitting time. For example, the ITUB4 experiment in the medium interval achieved the largest improvement, averaging $6.58\times$ faster than the sequential version. In addition to reduced overhead, model fitting becomes faster because the dataset size is substantially smaller.

The high standard deviation in medium-length parallel experiments is partially attributable to worker initialization overhead. The first execution consistently incurs 3-4 seconds of additional cost for process spawning and library imports. This penalty represents 20 – 50% of total execution time for small datasets. In production environments with persistent worker pools, this cold-start effect would be amortized across multiple tasks, yielding more consistent performance.

Instabilities in the time series also affect overall performance. Highly volatile assets such as PETR4 increase the time needed to identify satisfactory ARIMA orders during fitting. These oscillations can turn order selection into a bottleneck, limiting achievable speed gains from parallelization. Lastly, we calculated the estimated parallel fraction of the algorithm using Amdahl’s Law. As seen in Table 3, medium-size periods benefit the most from parallelism, with parallel fractions over 70% in each case.

Figure 2: Comparison between ARIMA forecasts and actual prices across different assets and time horizons.

Values slightly exceeding the theoretical limit ($f > 1$) result from system-level variability such as caching effects, process initialization overhead, and CPU scheduling, which may cause observed speedups to temporarily surpass idealized bounds.

Table 3: Estimated parallel fraction (f) using Amdahl’s Law ($N = 6$).

Asset	Period	Speedup (S)	Parallel Fraction (f)
ITUB4	Very long	1.05 ± 0.003	0.06
ITUB4	Long	1.40 ± 0.04	0.34
ITUB4	Medium	6.58 ± 2.50	1.02
PETR4	Very long	1.07 ± 0.002	0.08
PETR4	Long	1.53 ± 0.06	0.42
PETR4	Medium	2.82 ± 0.66	0.77
TAE11	Very long	1.07 ± 0.02	0.08
TAE11	Long	1.35 ± 0.03	0.31
TAE11	Medium	3.40 ± 0.90	0.85

6 Identified Limitations

The experimental evaluation is subject to several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the results. First, the pipeline was validated on only three Brazilian assets from a single national market, which limits the generalizability of the findings to other markets, asset classes, or economic contexts. Second, all experiments were conducted on a personal workstation with a six core CPU, and the observed speedups may differ substantially on systems with more cores, more RAM and memory bandwidth, or persistent worker pools that eliminate cold-start overhead. Third, the grid search evaluates all combinations exhaustively, which guarantees finding the global optimum within the defined search space but does not scale well to larger parameter ranges or more complex model families such as SARIMA or ARIMAX. Replacing exhaustive search with directed methods such as Bayesian optimization could reduce computational cost while maintaining selection quality.

7 Conclusion

The literature on ARIMA and its application to financial time series was reviewed, and an automated forecasting pipeline was implemented that integrates stationarity testing, parallelized grid search for hyperparameter selection, and a rolling one-step ahead forecast procedure. The pipeline operationalizes parameter selection and model fitting in a reproducible manner.

Experiments on ITUB4, PETR4, and TAE11 validated the grid search procedure: the method consistently selected parameter orders that yielded low forecasting errors for medium-length intervals, with MAPE below 3%, and reasonable RMSE and MAE values across the evaluated assets. Results indicate that ARIMA models produce competitive forecasts on shorter to medium windows but degrade on long historical horizons, particularly for highly volatile assets.

From a computational perspective, parallelizing the grid search reduced wall-clock time for hyperparameter optimization. The maximum observed speedup was $6.58\times$ for the ITUB4 medium interval experiment. The geometric mean speedup across experiments was $1.74\times$. Speedup was limited for very long series because overhead and the sequential cost of repeated refitting in the rolling forecast procedure reduce the fraction of execution time that benefits from parallel hyperparameter search.

7.1 Future Works

Future work will address both predictive robustness and scalability. On the modeling side, hybrid approaches that combine ARIMA with machine learning components, for example, ARIMA-LSTM or ARIMA-XGBoost, merit investigation. On the computational side, adapting the pipeline to GPU and distributed environments may increase scalability. Potential directions include prototype implementations using CUDA and deployment on distributed processing frameworks such as Apache Spark to enable concurrent analysis of multiple assets. Finally, replacing exhaustive grid search with more efficient hyperparameter optimization methods, such as evolutionary algorithms or Bayesian optimization, can further reduce computational cost while maintaining or improving model selection quality.

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